

PSBs - A Nimble Goliath or Engine of Economic Growth? (A Study with Reference to Public Sector Banks)

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Introduction

In recent times, Public Sector Banks (PSBs) have become a subject matter of discussion and debate. Still there is hue and cry about the performance of public sector banks, otherwise called State run banks. In this backdrop the present paper is an earnest attempt on the part of the authors to outline the performance of the PSBs and a few grey areas of concern. Incidentally the authors outline a few suggestions.

Nature of Study

The present study is mainly descriptive. However, relevant data are given to substantiate the theoretical information. The authors have not collected any data afresh. They have completely relied upon the secondary data i.e. published information. It is, therefore, an ex-post facto research.

Banking Sector

Banking sector plays a vital role in the economic development of a nation. This sector has generated huge employment opportunities.

Types

In India, there are two primary types of banking sector

- Public Sector Banks
- Private Sector Banks

Public Sector Banks

As implied by name, the government holds a major share in the capital of such banks. They are popularly known as nationalised banks or state run banks. There are 18 nationalised banks in India.

Private Sector Banks

As implied by name, the private sector banks are owned and controlled by a few prominent promoter groups. During 1990s, they gained momentum as a result of LPG (Liberalisation, Privatisation and Globalisation) policy of the government. They compete with public sector banks in India.

However, there is a common thread. Both private sector banks and public sector banks are regulated by RBI.

Scope of the Study

This paper gets itself confined to the study of public sector banks. For comparative study purpose, performance of private sector bank is briefly outlined.

Historical Perspective of PSBs

19th July, 1969 marks a milestone in Indian banking sector. On this day, the then Congress Government, headed by Smt. Indira Gandhi took a bold decision to nationalise 14 major scheduled commercial banks with deposits of over Rs.50 crore.

The primary objective of nationalisation was to break the vice-like grip of leaders of Commerce and Industry on commercial banking. This grip was likely to cause erosion of the capital base of such banks.

Subsequent to nationalisation of these 14 banks, some private sector banks were noticed to suffer from governance problems. Accordingly, six banks – Andhra Bank, Corporation Bank, New Bank of India, Oriental Bank of Commerce, Punjab and Sind Bank with deposit liability of Rs. 200 crore and above were nationalised in April 1980. With the nationalisation of these six banks, the number of public sector banks (PSBs) including State Bank of India and the associate banks, rose to 28 in April 1980.

Rationale of Study

In spite of the opening up of the banking sector to private players in the early 1990, PSBs still remain formidable players in the banking scene. The market share in overall bank credit and overall bank deposits was at 6.32 percent and 66.9 percent respectively at the end of fiscal year 2018-19.

The efficacy of bank nationalisation could be seen in the increase in bank branches brought about by the 22 public sector banks in just five years. Half of the 10,543 new branches opened between 1969 and 1975 were in the rural areas. It increased the share of rural branches from 17 percent to 36 percent. By 1990, total bank branches numbered 59,752 with over 58 percent share of rural branches. The share of agriculture in total credit went up from 2.2 percent in 1967 to over 9 percent in 1975.

There is another interesting information in favour of nationalisation. Between 1947 and 1955, there were 361 instances of bank failures. As such, many depositors lost their life savings and their faith in banking system. After 1955, there was a growth in deposit mobilisation. However, several problems persisted. The then private owners of the banks were merely interested in cornering the finance mobilised through depositors. They did not even care for running the banks on sound commercial principles. This resulted in a gradual erosion in the capital base of banks with the ratio of paid up capital and reserves to deposits declining from 9.7 percent in 1951 to 2.2 percent in 1969. Hence nationalisation.

There is another argument in support of public sector banks. They are confronted with formidable problems like increase in Non-performing Assets (NPAs), operational inefficiency and low profitability. In spite of this, it is commendable to note that not (even) a single nationalised

bank has failed or faced liquidation till date, unlike its pre-1969 predecessors in the private sector. Hence the present study.

Grey Areas

Having outlined the importance of PSBs, the authors now wish to outline a few areas of concern or grey areas. PSBs are not an unmixed blessing. Of late, they face the following formidable problems.

- Competition From Private Sector
- Regulatory hassles
- Threat from other agencies
- Bank charges
- Frauds
- Mounting bad loans (NPAs)
- Threat from Unions

Competition from Private Sector

Public sector banks cannot be compared with private sector banks. Recently, C.H. Venkatachalam, General Secretary of All India Bank Employees Association (AIBEA) has observed: “..... One cannot compare PSBs with private banks, as profit is the main objective of private banks while public banks have more of a social responsibility.”

Recently Shri Uday Kotak, Executive Vice-Chairman and Managing Director of Kotak Mahindra Bank has observed. “Private sector banks’ market share will go up significantly. They will be on par with that of public sector banks in the next five years.” The Catholic Syrian Bank Ltd., Chairman has observed: “Public sector banks grant loans. We (private sector banks) sell a loan.” Nowadays public sector banks face severe competition from private sector banks.

Regulatory Hassles

In India the RBI issues orders, now and then, regulating banking sector. Accordingly the banks have to reduce the deposit interest rates. This adds fuel to the fire.

Threat From Other Agencies

Once three C’s were associated with the banking sector. They are “Capital, Capacity and Character.” Now the public sector banks have been fearing of 3Cs. They are Comptroller and Auditor General of India (CAG), Central Vigilance Commission (CVC) and Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI).

The Commissioner of CVC has recently observed; “CVC is reviewing central statutory reports, concurrent auditors’ reports and other audit reports through Central Vigilance Officers of all public sector banks and insurance companies.”

Bank Charges

The news in Business Line dated 22nd December 2018 is worth reading: “ Twenty one (then) public sector banks have collected more than Rs10000 crore in 42 months from the general public for not maintaining minimum balance and charges for additional ATM transactions beyond the permitted free facility. The following table illustrates this.

Table:1 Collection Through Charges (Rs. In Crore)

Years	Charges for not maintaining minimum balance (Rs. in crore)	Charges for ATM use beyond permitted free numbers (Rs. in crore)	Total (Rs. in crore)
2015-16	841.41	921.64	1763.05
2016-17	926.36	938.13	1864.49
2017-18	3489.52	1413.29	4902.81
2018-19*	989.45	871.93	1861.38
Grand Total			10391.73

Source Lok Sabha * April To September

These charges contribute to banks' profitability. However, the customers of banks are not likely to be happy.

Frauds

Frauds in banking sector have become the order of the day. A total of 8,802 frauds were reported by scheduled commercial banks and public sector banks in 2017-18 against 7,794 in 2016-17 and 7,482 in 2015-16. Thus there is an increasing trend. The amount lost in crores erode the profitability of these banks, causing concern to the depositors.

According to tech major CISCO, banking and finance, government and critical infrastructure were among the most targeted sectors in India by cyber criminals in 2018-19. This is likely to create panic in the minds of customers.

Mounting Bad Loans

Recently, the term NPA is occupying central place in all news papers. It means non-performing assets. If a bank loan is due for more than 6 months, it is termed as non-performing asset.

As per RBI provisional data on global operations, as on 31.3.2019, the aggregate amount of gross NPAs of PSBs was Rs. 8,06,412 crore.

The banks have to create provision against such risk which in turn erodes the profitability. This is not in the interest of the investors.

Threat From Trade Unions

The recent announcement by the Government about merger of PSBs have been vehemently criticised by the trade unions. Recently, Shri Devidas Tuljapurkar, Joint Secretary of All India Bank Employees Association (AIBEA) has observed:

“By kickstarting consolidation among PSBs and at the same time opening doors to the private sector, there is an attempt to undermine PSBs.

Suggestions

Having outlined the problems faced by public sector banks, the authors now outline a few remedial measures.

- To curb the incidence of huge NPAs, the banks can cross check the information by the borrowers with some agencies like credit rating agencies.
- Regarding vacancies at the top level, the concerned bank should not allow the top post to fall vacant for a long period of time.

- They should get regular feedback from customers.
- They must arrange for discussion with trade unions' representatives at a periodical interval of at least one year.

Conclusion

Public sector banks have made some objectives of nationalisation realistic. Yet they are confronted with formidable problems, which they need to be addressed with care and caution. Otherwise Public sector banks are likely to become Pathetic Sick Banks. The RBI must issue guidelines in the interest of the nation and gullible investors. The authors still have a ray of hope that Public sector banks will become stronger in the near future.